

THE EDUCATIONAL SIGNIFICANCE OF USING INTERACTIVE TECHNIQUES IN THE PRIMARY CLASS READING LESSON

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Abstract: this article highlights the positive importance of using pedagogical technologies and new interactive methods in conducting reading lessons in primary grades. Also, examples of interactive methods are recommended and explained.

Key words: primary class, reading, interactive, interpretive reading, intonation, method, education, expressive reading, artistic reading.

The mother tongue, mathematics, reading, etiquette, and natural science classes held in primary classes have a special place in the educational system according to their essence, goals and tasks. After all, the foundations of literacy and moral-educational education stand on their soil. Therefore, it is necessary to pay special attention to increase the interest of students in primary education classes. Because children should not get tired of the sacred word "*lesson*" from the elementary grades. Today, experienced teachers use various didactic games to increase students' interest in lessons. Interactive method - by increasing the activity between the teacher and students in the educational process, they guarantee the assimilation of knowledge under the influence of their interaction, and serve to develop personal qualities. The use of these methods improves the quality and efficiency of the lesson. Its main criteria are informal discussions, free presentation of educational material, independent reading, learning, conducting seminars, creating opportunities for students to take initiative, small groups, large groups, It consists of assignments, assignments, written works, etc. for working as a class team.

Interactivity is the activity of two people, that is, the learning process takes place in the form of a dialogue (*computer communication*) or on the basis of teacher-student interactions. Interactivity - mutual activity, movement, affectiveness, student-teacher, student-student conversations occur. The main goal of interactive methods is to create an environment for the active, free, creative thinking of the student, to use his needs, interests, internal capabilities by creating the most favorable environment and situation for the educational process. Such classes are conducted in such a way that no student is left out in this process, and they have the opportunity to clearly express

their opinions that they have heard, read, and seen. A process of mutual exchange of ideas is created. Children's enthusiasm and interest in learning increases, mutual friendly relations are formed. According to its nature, interactive education is based on didactic games, heuristic (*thinking, searching, finding*) dialogue - creating and solving a problem situation by designing the lesson process - learning the methods of implementation using information and communication technologies based on creativity.

Education on the basis of information and communication technologies, in turn, consists of teaching with the help of computer programs, distance learning, teaching on the basis of Internet networks, media - educational methods. In primary education, methods based on the design of heuristic conversations through didactic games according to the age characteristics, literacy levels, and personal nature of students are widely used. If in the process of teaching, every student worked on assignments at the level of his/her ability to learn, he/she would have ensured high quality and efficiency. Such a situation can be realized only through differentiated education. Now let's think about the implementation of educational processes through didactic games: Interactive game methods are based on the activation and acceleration of student activity. They are of great importance in identifying and implementing practical solutions for the realization and development of the student's creative potential. The main types of interactive games are: intellectual (*intelligent*) and active and mixed games. These help students to develop intellectual, physical, moral, spiritual, educational, psychological, aesthetic, artistic, entrepreneurial, creative, work, and professional skills.

This method leads the student to activate his inner capabilities, to think, to think freely, to communicate, and to be creative. In particular, it increases interest in learning about the environment, life, challenges, how to overcome obstacles, and develops critical thinking skills.

Certain topics included in the "*Reading Book*" lessons of the primary grade are determined by the fact that they bring students to the magical world of fiction, and focus on the correct formation of their worldviews based on the ideology of national independence. Accordingly, reading The main feature of the classes is to ensure students' literacy, and to educate them in the spirit of high moral values based on the national ideology. united within common themes such as nature, seasons, folklore, love of work, major holiday dates, national independence and spirituality.

The topics chosen for the reading lessons are intended to provide students with knowledge and education on everyday life, strengthening of independence and human relations. Among them, the themes of independence, homeland, spirituality and nature stand out. Their goal is self-awareness, to awaken feelings related to independence, homeland and nature. Unlike other stages of continuous education, the formation of students' reading skills, working on the text of the work is the didactic goal of education in primary school reading classes. It is closely connected with spiritual-moral, literary-aesthetic education by working on texts on various topics. Particular attention is paid to the variety of genres, poetic perfection of the texts selected for each topic in the textbooks, and their compatibility with the students' knowledge level and age characteristics. It is one of the important tasks of teachers to make students understand that the knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired with the help of textbooks will be necessary in the future life.

Implementation of the requirements for reading education in the DTS and "Mother tongue" curriculum for primary education, proper organization of classroom learning, teaching stages, principles and methods, first of all, are largely dependent on the appropriate use of advanced pedagogical technologies.

In general, the didactic tasks set before the reading classes are as follows:

- ❖ *Good reading qualities in students: formation of correct, fast, conscious, expressive reading.*
- ❖ *To teach students to use the book, to get the necessary knowledge from it, to instill a love for the book; to raise them from a casual reader to a thoughtful, creative reader.*
- ❖ *Expanding and enriching students' knowledge about the environment and forming their scientific outlook.*
- ❖ *Educating students to be morally, aesthetically mature and in the spirit of love for work.*
- ❖ *Cultivating students' connected speech and literary-aesthetic thinking.*
- ❖ *Enriching the imagination of students.*
- ❖ *Formation of elementary literary ideas.*

It should not be forgotten that there are specific and scientific methodical methods of performing each educational task, which are being enriched by modern teaching methods. These tasks are solved in relation to others and in the course of study activities outside the classroom.

Reading is important in human life. Through reading, a person acquires knowledge about existence and society, a person who does not know how to read is no different from a blind person. In the primary class, reading activities are carried out in all subject classes. But he develops a method of teaching to read. Achievements in the field of general development, psychology, and private methodology of reading methodology are formed on the basis of the achievements of all subjects.

Methods used in reading lessons. In the "National Program of Personnel Training", advanced pedagogical technologies of education, creation of modern teaching-methodical complexes are emphasized as one of the main tasks of general secondary education. clearly defines the scope of teacher and student activities. Reading activities, which are important in human life, are carried out in all subject classes. Study methodology is improved on the basis of achievements in the field of general development of young students, psychology, and special methodology. The effectiveness of study lessons largely depends on the correct selection of educational methods. Consequently, the science Teaching methods such as zi are also constantly developing. For example, in old schools, reading was taught on the basis of rote memorization, but now it is conducted on the basis of explanatory reading. Usually, no attention is paid to commenting on the words in the text, explaining their meaning, retelling what was read, and in general, making the reading conscious. They include more correct pronunciation, recitation, expressive reading.

Now that reading in schools is conducted based on the method of explanatory reading, the following question arises: What is explanatory reading? Interpretive reading was founded by the Russian pedagogue K. D. Ushinsky in the 60s and 70s of the 19th century. reading". Successors of the work of K. D. Ushinsky introduced innovations to the method of explanatory reading. Korf and Vakhterev say that interpretive reading is a means of providing students with real knowledge, while Vodovozov and Bunakov put forward the opinion that knowledge is given to students in the process of reading in connection with the analysis of the artistic work and the educational character of the work. Annotated reading will be successful only if the following principles are fully followed:

Organization of study in connection with life. Basing on students' life experiences and impressions for conscious and effective reading. Visual organization of study, organization of excursions to nature and historical

places, observation of animal and plant world, introduction to pictures, tables, objects and conducting the text in the way of expressive reading of the student. In elementary school reading lessons, poems, parables, fairy tales, stories, legends, proverbs and riddles, popular scientific works are studied. Naturally, each of them is created in its own form, style and content. That is why it is necessary to study the works of each genre in a unique way.

Artistic reading. Literary reading is the highest stage of expressive reading. All components of speech art are involved in it. It requires the reader to get into the essence of the work, read it artistically. In literary reading, it is possible to achieve impressiveness only when the mental state and experiences of the heroes of the work are fully understood. The use of audio-video tapes of actors' performances in preparation for artistic studies is very effective. One of the factors that ensure the success of literary reading is selective reading. For example, in the 3rd grade, in the process of getting acquainted with the story "Hassa" by H. Tokhtaboyev, Shavkat's answers to the questions of grandfather Kabul or the episode of children's argument in the story "Bahs" by S. Anorboyev, choosing these places according to the teacher's assignment as a result of re-reading, a deeper understanding of the artistic and aesthetic value of these works is achieved.

Search method. This method is widely used in creating questions for readers based on events and details in the work, and evaluating characters. The reproductive method is widely used in reading classes. For example, in the first lessons, the teacher divides the text of the work into parts, draws the attention of the students to the important idea that the writer or poet wants to say, defines it, together with the students, the meaning assigned to the image means open and help students. All this serves as a guide for students. After that, the students independently perform the tasks indicated above with the help of the teacher's instructions.

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